

CLIMATE CHANGE REPORTING IN PAKISTANI NEWSPAPERS: EXPLORING THE PREDOMINANT THEMES

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Abstract

Climate change stands as one of the most persistent challenges confronting the contemporary world. Its adverse impacts are disproportionately severe for poorer and developing nations, where limited resources exacerbate vulnerability. Pakistan, consistently ranked among the countries most affected by climate change, faces a wide spectrum of consequences ranging from intensifying heatwaves and recurrent floods to accelerated glacial melt, all of which threaten human life, biodiversity, and ecological stability in the region. In this context, the media assumes a pivotal role in raising public awareness, shaping and framing environmental discourses, and sensitizing policymakers and think tanks toward sustainable environmental practices. Nonetheless, existing scholarship suggests that the scope, depth, and framing of climate change reporting in Pakistan remain limited and often fall short of meeting the urgency of the crisis. Employing a well-designed and tested code book we have conducted a deductive thematic analysis to explore and analyze the predominant themes available in the climate change reporting given by the prominent Pakistani newspapers during April 15th to May 14th, 2025. Our findings show that the news reports contained themes such as; “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events”, “Economic Implications”, “Policy and Governance”, “Public Awareness and Education”, “Climate Justice and Social Inequality”, and “International Climate Discourse and Pakistan”, “International Climate Discourse and Pakistan”.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is no longer a distant concern; it has emerged as one of the most urgent challenges confronting humanity. For poorer and developing nations, the situation is particularly alarming because limited economic, technological, and institutional resources make it harder to cope with the damage.

Pakistan, listed among the countries most vulnerable to climate change, experiences a wide range of impacts – from punishing heatwaves and flash floods to rapid glacial melt – each posing serious threats to human life, biodiversity, and the stability of ecosystems (IPCC, 2023; Kreft et al., 2021).

In such circumstances, the role of the media becomes critical – not only in raising public awareness but also in shaping discourse, influencing public opinion, and pushing policymakers and think tanks toward meaningful environmental action (Anderson, 2017; Shanahan, 2009). However, several studies suggest that climate change coverage in Pakistan often remains limited in scope and depth, failing to match the urgency of the crisis (Yousaf & Ali, 2020). This gap makes it essential to explore the extent and quality of climate change reporting in national newspapers, both in terms of thematic focus and framing approaches.

Climate change refers to long-term alterations in Earth's climate patterns. Human activities such as burning fossil fuels, large-scale deforestation, and intensive industrial production have significantly increased greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere, trapping heat and raising global temperatures (Hassan et al., 2024). This trend is expected to continue if mitigation measures remain inadequate. The consequences are far-reaching: rising temperatures, more intense and frequent storms, altered rainfall patterns, sea-level rise, and shifting ocean currents. These changes disrupt water availability, agriculture, energy production, public health, and biodiversity, making climate change one of the most pressing global challenges that demand immediate action to reduce emissions and adapt to impacts.

Research shows that climate change, driven primarily by anthropogenic factors, is intensifying the frequency and severity of extreme events such as droughts, hurricanes, and floods. These shifts threaten not only ecosystems and biodiversity but also human health, food security, and financial stability. As glaciers melt and sea levels rise, vulnerable communities face heightened risks of displacement and resource scarcity (Rawat et al., 2024). The agricultural sector, particularly in developing regions, is highly sensitive to these environmental disruptions.

In Pakistan's context, climate change impacts on agriculture are already evident. Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns make it more difficult to grow crops, while oceanic changes are harming fisheries and marine life. Natural disasters such as floods and droughts occur more frequently and with greater intensity, disproportionately

affecting indigenous and low-income communities. The economic consequences are equally severe, with high recovery costs and income losses in key industries like agriculture and tourism (Yanagi, 2024).

Among crops, wheat holds particular significance as a staple food for much of the world's population. Its growth is highly sensitive to climatic conditions, making it vulnerable to unpredictable rainfall and rising temperatures. Higher temperatures can shorten the wheat growing cycle, reduce soil moisture, and negatively affect grain quality – including starch and protein content – which in turn impacts gluten strength and bread-making qualities. Warmer conditions also facilitate the spread of pests and diseases, compounding the threat to both yield and quality (Yanagi, 2024). Drought conditions intensify these challenges, stressing plants during critical reproductive phases and leading to reduced pollination, lower grain development, and ultimately decreased yields.

To address these threats, agricultural stakeholders are adopting adaptive strategies such as developing drought- and heat-resistant wheat varieties, improving irrigation efficiency, and promoting sustainable farming practices. However, the pace of adaptation remains slower than the accelerating impacts of climate change, making further research and policy support vital. Beyond the agricultural dimension, the role of media in climate change communication is central. Mass media serve as the primary bridge between scientific communities, policymakers, and the public. By framing issues, shaping narratives, and disseminating reliable information, media can foster environmental awareness and influence policy agendas (Ashraf & Islam, 2014, as cited in Jan et al., 2020). In Pakistan, the media have been instrumental in agenda-setting, connecting citizens with policymakers, and drawing attention to critical issues such as water and food security, public health, and energy sustainability (Hanan et al., 2016, as cited in Jan et al., 2020).

Different forms of media, from traditional outlets like newspapers, radio, and television to digital and social media platforms, each play distinct roles. Television remains the dominant source of information for urban populations, while rural communities often rely more on radio. Despite its importance, climate change reporting in Pakistan's mainstream print

media remains limited in depth and frequency (Kakade et al., 2013). Similar patterns are observed globally, where local and regional media outlets, although crucial in providing context-specific environmental information, often lack the resources, training, and editorial independence necessary for comprehensive coverage (Corner, 2011, as cited in Kakade et al., 2013).

Scholars have emphasized that sustainable development requires responsible environmental practices and sustained public engagement. Media coverage that is accessible, credible, and science-informed can help cultivate environmental literacy, strengthen public pressure on policymakers, and encourage behavioral changes necessary to mitigate and adapt to climate change (Shanahan, 2011, as cited in Kakade et al., 2013). However, challenges such as political interference, economic instability, and inadequate journalist training continue to undermine the potential of media to serve as effective agents of climate change communication (Kakade et al., 2013).

According to Jan et al. (2020) the climate change (CC) poses a gradually server threat to nations with vulnerable environmental condition and socio economic, like Pakistan. In the spit of worldwide concern, public awareness and literacy about CC in Pakistan remain critically low, undermining adaptive capacity and national resilience. Particularly their study focuses on the limitation and contribution of media, lady health worker, educational institution, civil society organization and local government structure in fostering climate consciousness. The research used the Culture Theory of Risk for nuanced accepting of media role and how people process media information based on their culture. Through the approach of mixed method combining content analysis, in-depth interview and survey, the study reveal systemic gaps in the communication that hinder people understanding of climate problem. It also emphases innovative grassroots struggle specially those involving women led outreach by participatory educational models and lady health workers that are bridging the knowledge gap in marginalized communities. The findings highlight the urgency of a coordinated national policy that leverage these diverse channels for climate action and education. The study concluded with strategy recommendations aimed at integrating climate literacy into public health

campaigns, school curricula and local government training, while also improving the effectiveness and accountability of civil society and media in portraying environmental discourse.

In an attempt to review the existing scholarship on Climate Change (CC), its implications on society and exploring different strategies to mitigate the effects of climate change Rawat et al. (2024) claimed that due to excessive human activities such as burning of various energy sources, deforestation, rapid and widespread urbanization and mismanagement of water resources, climate change become a huge threat and challenge to the world. Such human activities have exacerbated the overall temperature of the globe affecting flora and fauna and the overall societal and human growth. The article aimed at exploring various types of effects of climate change in different sectors such as agriculture, economy, tourism, biodiversity, forest ecosystem, sea level rise, water resources and human health. The researchers, by applying systematic method, collected data with the help of 20 most used keywords related to environmental change. For the exploration of changes in climate the study found numerous climate models designed to predict weather patterns before any potential risk by curbing and improving the overall effects of climate change in various sectors such as agriculture, sea level rise, tourism, human health and water crisis. However, utilizing climate models the world must go for adaptation and mitigation strategies to reduce the impact of weather patterns. Similarly, the researchers urged for awareness regarding adaptation and mitigation strategies in workplaces and daily routine.

Keeping in view the pertinence and urgency of the topic understudy and the literature reviewed, we have devised a broader research question;

What are the predominant themes produced by the selected newspapers; *Dawn*, *Daily Times*, *The News International*, in their climate change reporting during the time period under study?

This broader research question has further been studied in terms of relatively more specific research questions such as;

- How newspapers are educating the public about the consequences of climate change, such as heatwaves, floods, droughts, and environmental degradation?

- How newspapers report on the government’s climate change policies, programs, and their effectiveness?
- Coverage of how climate change is exacerbating water scarcity, food security and malnutrition in Pakistan?
- How the media frames climate change as a challenge for achieving sustainable development goals in Pakistan?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Framing theory is a significant theoretical underpinning that helps the researchers to intellectualize and contextualize what is being produced by the media as ‘frames’ regarding some pressing issue in a society. It is important to dig out the framing of an issue because the way media frames an issue has an impact on the audience. This theory helps the researchers to determine how specific frames are built and disseminated to influence target audience (Entman, 1993).

Although, the framing is widely used to study politics, as it plays a key role in how citizens view elections, political parties, and government policies. By studying how different media outlets frame issues, researchers can understand biases, identify patterns, and explore the impact of media on public opinion. For example, during an election campaign, candidates often use framing to present themselves positively, emphasizing their achievements and downplaying their weaknesses (Scheufele, 1999). However, the framing theory is also applied in studies of social issues, such as climate change, gender equality, and racial justice. By analyzing how media frames these topics, researchers can see how issues are portrayed and politicized. For instance, the media's framing of climate change might emphasize its scientific backing, economic costs, or political debates, each frame leading to different understandings of the problem.

So, keeping in view the appropriateness of the framing theory with our research objective, we have employed this theory deductively to explore and analyze various themes/frames produced by the Pakistani newspapers in their climate change reporting during the time period under study.

RESEARCH DESIGN & METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

For this study the researchers found 79 news stories regarding climate change in the *Daily Times*, 53 news stories each in daily *Dawn* and *The News International* by applying the key words and search mechanism employed in this study the time period under study i.e. April 14th to May 14th, 2025. After employing data cleansing, we found 09 news stories relevant to the objectives of this study in *Daily Times*, 13 in *Dawn*, and 12 in daily *The News International*. As a next step to select an appropriate and manageable sample size, we employed lottery method within the premise of probability sampling and selected two news stories from each newspaper.

The data has been collected using keywords including; "Climate Change" "Global Warming" "floods" "flash floods" "terrestrial rains" "torrential rains" "land sliding" "glacier melting" "Hail Storm", past one month, only in headline/title, news stories. We have collected data from the official websites of the selected newspapers through ‘Advanced Google Search’ using; (allintitle: "Climate Change" site:https://dailytimes.com.pk/), (allintitle: "Climate Change" site:https://www.dawn.com/), and (allintitle: "Climate Change" site:https://www.thenews.com.pk/) respectively.

Data Analysis

For the sake of data analysis, keeping in view the broader research question and research objective, we have employed thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) deductively. We have a broader theme under study i.e. ‘climate change’ reporting in Pakistan and we have delimited this construct into smaller and measurable concepts i.e. themes and sub-themes as shown in the following coding sheet for clarity and for comprehensive thematic analysis.

For this coding sheet we have extracted key words for thematization from Six English newspapers (*Daily Times*, *Dawn*, *The Nation*, *The Express Tribune*, *The News International* and *Pakistan Today*). Two stories each from every newspaper and seven from *Dawn*. A total 08 main themes and 15 sub-themes were identified. Each story was tallied against all main & sub-themes.

Coding Sheet

Theme	Sub-Theme	Keywords/ Coding Units
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.1 Floods and Heatwaves	Dust Storm, Heavy Rain, Wind Storm, Hot Weather, Heatwaves, 88% Humidity, Weather Intervention, Flash Floods. Hailstorm, Collapse of Giant Glaciers
	1.2 Human Losses	Malnutrition, Mortality, Hospitals Overwhelmed, Heatstroke Deaths,
	1.3 Role of NGOs and Civil Society	Rescue Team, Dewatering Pumps, Public Concerns, Survey Flood-Affected Areas, IMF Condition
2. Impacts on Agriculture	2.1 Agricultural Vulnerability	Rain-Fed Agriculture, Lack of Resilient Crop Varieties, Agricultural Productivity Reduction, Food Security
	2.2 Water Scarcity and Management	Govt Negligence and Irrigation Mismanagement, Rainfall Disrupted Threshing, Wet Crop Needs Drying, Water Scarcity, Per Capita Water Availability, Drought-Stricken, River Drying
3. Economic Implications	3.1 Economic Impact of Climate Change	Economic Loss, GDP Decline, Infrastructure Damage, Landslides, Stranded Tourists, Agricultural Productivity Reduction.
	3.2 Climate Change as a Barrier to Development	Scorching Heat, Power Outages, Water Supply Failure, Public Health Risk, Infrastructure Stress. Landslides, Disrupted Access, Stranded Tourists, Rainfall, Disaster Management,
4. Climate Justice and Social Inequality	4.1 Vulnerable Populations	Local Farmers Suffering, Neglected by Government, Climate-Led Displacement, Food Insecurity, Marginalized Communities, Rescue Challenges, Rural Hardship, Rural Farmer Support, Limited Resources

Theme	Sub-Theme	Keywords/ Coding Units
5. Policy and Governance	5.1 Government Response and Action	Government's Failure to Manage and Develop Agriculture Sector, Imposed Heavy Taxes, Formers Being Exploited and Deprived, Consensus-Driven Policies, Govt Institutions' Response and Preparedness.
	5.2 International Cooperation	Need For International Cooperation, Compensation, Global Climate Discussions, IMF Conditions, Climate-Based Project Selection, Carbon Tax, WMO and NMHSS

		Collaboration, Climate Risk Planning, Monsoon Forecast
	5.3 Disaster Preparedness and Response	Patrolling by Field Staff, Power Supply Disrupted, Circuits Tripped, Power Companies Response, Preparedness, Extreme Weather, Disaster Management Authorities, Carbon Tax
6. Public Awareness and Education	6.1 Media's Role in Raising Awareness	Awareness Through Different Activities Like Sports, Public Engagement, Youth-Led Discussions, Environmental Education, Train Farmers, Local Agriculture Advice, Climate-Resilient Crops, Traditional Farming, Genetic Modified Crops, Adaptation Strategies, Digital Knowledge sharing, Low-Cost Water Conservation Method
	6.2 Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives	Tectonic Plates, Earth's Internal Structure, Latitude and Longitude Diagrams, Understanding Earth's Dynamics, WMO Forecast, ENSO, Snow Cover Impact, Scientific Assessment, Met Office Warnings.
7. International Climate Discourse and Pakistan	7.1 Climate Change in Global Context	Pakistan's Role, International Agreements, Global Climate Discussions, National Responsibilities, Plantation Drive, Green Partnerships
8. Media Framing and Representation	8.1 Framing of Climate Change	Intense and Oddly Refreshing, Dramatic Spell, Break from the Heat, Unexpected Weather, "Pellets Form Sky" "Hail Like Squash/Tennis Ball"

FINDINGS & ANALYSIS

Following pages contain deductive thematic analysis of the selected news stories from daily *Dawn*;

"More hail, thunderstorms likely from today". (2025, April 18). *Dawn*. Retrieved from; <https://www.dawn.com/news/1904947>

Theme	Sub-theme	Keywords / Coding Units
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.1 Floods and Heatwaves	Heat waves, extreme weather alert, thunderstorms, NDMA advisory, cyclones, rainfall.
	1.2 Human Losses	Deaths by lightning, damaged houses, agricultural losses, public precautions, NDMA report
	1.3 Role of NGOs and Civil Society	NDMA emergency operations, Rescue 1122, PDMA operations.
2. Impacts on Agriculture	2.1 Agricultural Vulnerability	Crop damage, lower yields, agricultural output.

3. Economic Implications	3.1 Economic Impact of Climate Change	Infrastructure damage, transport disruption, reduced crop yield.
4. Climate Justice and Social Inequality	4.1 Vulnerable Populations	Rural deaths, infrastructure loss, heat wave impact.
5. Policy and Governance	5.1 Government Response and Action	NDMA advisories, PDMA updates, commissioner instructions.
	5.3 Disaster Preparedness and Response	Standby emergency teams, Rescue 1122, warning apps, public instructions.
6. Public Awareness and Education	6.1 Media's Role in Raising Awareness	NDMA advisory, NEOC advisory, safety tips, emergency instructions, heat protection guide.
	6.2 Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives	Heat wave predictions, temperature projections, scientific alerts
8. Media Framing and Representation	8.1 Framing of Climate Change	Extreme weather, freak storm, soaring temperatures, searing heat, disaster warnings.

Interpretation and Analysis:

The researchers have interpreted the data using thematic analysis deductively through coding units from the news item from *Dawn* news matching eight themes of Climate Change. Matching it to Theme 1 of “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events”, the researcher found match with all three sub themes i.e. Floods and Heat waves, Human Losses, Role of NGOs and Civil Society having words of Heat waves, extreme weather alert, thunderstorms, NDMA advisory, cyclones, and rainfall. The researchers further matched the Theme 2 “Impacts on Agriculture” with key words Crop damage, lower yields, agricultural output falling into subtheme of Agricultural Vulnerability. The key words from the news story picked by researcher reflect economic threats to infrastructure and food security. The words in the news story like damage, transport disruption and reduced crop yield fall under the Theme 3 “Economic Implications” and sub theme Economic Impact of Climate Change. The Theme 4 of the coding sheet when matched with the coding words present in the story like rural deaths, infrastructure loss and heat wave impact cover the sub theme Vulnerable Populations.

Theme 5 of the coding sheet “Policy and Governance” is also covered in the news items along with two sub themes Government Response and Action, and Disaster Preparedness and Response with key words like Standby emergency teams, Rescue 1122, warning apps, public instructions, NDMA advisories, PDMA

updates and commissioner instructions. Theme 6 of the coding sheet “Public Awareness and Education” with sub themes Media's Role in Raising Awareness and Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives were covered in the news story with key words like heat wave predictions, temperature projections, scientific alerts, NDMA advisory, NEOC advisory, safety tips, emergency instructions and heat protection guide. There were no key words related to Theme 7 of the coding sheet. The Theme 8 of the sheet “Media Framing and Representation” along with sub theme Framing of Climate Change with key words in the news story like Extreme weather, freak storm, soaring temperatures, searing heat and disaster warnings.

The news story in the *Dawn* mainly focused on Casualties and Heat wave alert in Punjab and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa provinces. It covers the reports on government preparedness and disaster alerts along with prediction of heat wave. It also issues advisory by the authorities like NDMA and NEOC about the extreme weather in different cities of Punjab along with a prediction of heat wave by the NDMA. The news story also covers the measures and advice for the citizens related to heat wave and extreme weather. The nine casualties reported in last two days of the reported time period and damaged infrastructure details were also discussed.

“Strong wind storm sweeps through Hyderabad, adjoining districts”. (2025, May 04). *Dawn*. Retrieved from; <https://www.dawn.com/news/1908287>

Theme	Sub-theme	Keywords / Coding Units
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.1 Floods and Heat waves	Wind Storm, Hot Weather/Heat waves, 88% Humidity
3. Economic Implications	3.2 Climate Change as a Barrier to Development	Scorching Heat, Power Outages, Water Supply Failure, Public Health Risk, Infrastructure Stress, Landslides, Disrupted Access, Stranded Tourists, Disaster Management
5. Policy and Governance	5.3 Disaster Preparedness and Response	Power Supply Disrupted, Circuits Tripped, Patrolling by Field Staff, Extreme Weather, Power Companies' Response

Interpretation and Analysis:

The researchers have interpreted the data using thematic analysis deductively through coding units from the news item from *Dawn* matching eight themes of Climate Change. Matching it to Theme 1 of “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events”, the researcher found match with all three sub themes i.e. Floods and Heat waves, Human Losses, Role of NGOs and Civil Society having words of Heat waves, extreme weather alert, thunderstorms, NDMA advisory, cyclones, and rainfall. The researcher further matched the Theme 2 “Impacts on Agriculture” with key words Crop damage, lower yields, agricultural output falling into subtheme of Agricultural Vulnerability. The key words from the news story picked by researcher reflect economic threats to infrastructure and food security. The words in the news story like damage, transport disruption and reduced crop yield fall under the Theme 3 “Economic Implications” and sub theme Economic Impact of Climate Change.

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with sub themes Media's Role in Raising Awareness and Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives were covered in the news story with key words like heat wave predictions, temperature projections, scientific alerts, NDMA advisory, NEOC advisory, safety tips, emergency instructions and heat protection guide. There were no key words related to Theme 7 of the coding sheet. The Theme 8 of the sheet “Media Framing and Representation” along with sub theme Framing of Climate Change with key words in the news story like Extreme weather, freak storm, soaring temperatures, searing heat and disaster warnings.

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Following pages contain deductive thematic analysis of the selected news stories from *Daily Times*; “Hailstorms cause damage and flash floods in Islamabad and KP”. (2025, April). *Daily Times*. Retrieved From; <https://dailytimes.com.pk/1287949/hailstorms-cause-damage-and-flash-floods-in-islamabad-and-kp/>

Themes	Sub Themes	Coding Units in News Report.
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.1 Floods and Heatwaves	Hail Strom, Flash Floods, Intense Rainfall, Dust Strom, relief from the heat, weather Pleasant, damage
	1.2 Human Losses	Child died, hospital, treatment, children, people, run home in fear
3. Economic Implications	3.2 Climate Change as a Barrier to Dev.	weather pleasant, solar panel damaged, power outages, restore electricity, PDMA
5. Policy and Governance	5.1 Government Response and Action	Readiness to respond effectively, prepared to manage the expected flood, PDMA, People should stay alert
	5.3 Disaster Preparedness and Response	power outages, restore electricity, affected several areas, PDMA, prepared to manage the expected flood
6. Public Awareness and Education	6.2 Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives	Pakistan Meteorological Department, Expects more rain, wind and thunderstorms

Interpretation and Analysis

It is the story having the head line hailstorm causes damage and flash floods in Islamabad and KP, published on April 16,2025 in *Daily Times*. This story was analyzed while using deductive thematic content analysis. A codebook having eight major themes with multiple sub themes was used for the analysis. The story which was studied thoroughly, only four major themes were detected in its content, and a total six sub themes were also identified.

The story narrated the tale of the hailstorm that cause damages in Islamabad and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The first theme identified on the codebook “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events”, was surfaced along with its subthemes “flood and heatwaves” and “human loses”. The themes were identified with the help of the coding units and the questions given in the codebook. This also help in identifying the themes presented in the story. The third major theme on the codebook “economic implication” was also found in the text of the story, but it has only its second subtheme ‘Climate Change as a Barrier to Development’. The story further had the components of the theme ‘policy and governance’. It is fifth theme on the codebook; the story covered its first ‘Government Response and Action’ and third ‘Disaster Preparedness and Response’ themes. The codebook sixth theme “public awareness and Education” was also found in the story text. The

content of the story could only match with its second theme ‘Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives.’

During the analysis the key words used in the story were tallied with the codebook keywords. It also helped in finding the underlying themes in the story. The actual numbers of the themes (according to the codebook) cand be read in the table above.

After a thorough analysis it was noted that the major themes in the story were the occurrence of the natural disasters like rainfall and hail storms and the damages (material and human) happened in the result of such natural calamities. The second, that how it helps also in neutralizing the harsh hot weather. The third major element seen was the response of the government agencies like WAPDA and PDMA, after the hailstorm. It narrates about their preparedness and rehabilitation activities. And the last major as well as important theme was about the public awareness before, during and after the disaster. It described that how Metrology and PDMA aware the people about the upcoming climate related risk situation.

“FM Ishaq Dar warns of rising regional tensions, calls for global cooperation”. (2025, May 06). *Daily Times*. Retrieved from; <https://dailytimes.com.pk/1296702/fm-ishaq-dar-warns-of-rising-regional-tensions-calls-for-global-cooperation/>

Themes	Sub Themes	Coding Units in News Report.
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.1 Floods and Heatwaves	“Catastrophic 2022 floods as a warning of future disasters”
4. Climate Justice and Social Inequality	4.1 Vulnerable Populations	“Disproportionate impact of climate change on vulnerable countries like Pakistan.” “Contributing minimally to global emissions, we remain among the top ten most vulnerable countries”
5. Policy and Governance	5.2 International Cooperation	Global cooperation

Interpretation and Analysis

This was the only story in our sample which was published in the month of May in 2025. When this *Daily Times* story was analyzed by deductive thematic content analysis technique, three major themes of the codebook were recognized. Each of the major themes has it’s only one subtheme found existing in the text of the story. The keywords given in the coding-book helped us to found all these themes in the story.

After through reading of the story, it was found that this text has a main focus of various regional tensions like, allegations regarding Pahalgam attack Indus water issue between India and Pakistan, Kashmir and Palestine issue, but it has a few very important mentions about the climate related issues.

It can be seen in the table above that the first major in the codebook “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events” was identified, but the story has it’s only one subtheme “floods and heatwaves” of the total three. This theme was identified when we read “catastrophic 2022 floods as a warning of future disasters.” The fourth codebook theme “Climate Justice and Social Inequality” was also found lying in the text of the story. It was carrying along with its only one subtheme “vulnerable population”. The sentences or clauses like “disproportionate impact of climate change on vulnerable countries like Pakistan” “contributing minimally to global emissions, we remain among the

top ten most vulnerable countries,” helped us to find the fourth theme in the text. The phrase in the headline “global cooperation” popup the fifth codebook theme “Policy and Governance” in my mind. The text actually pointing it at its second subtheme “International cooperation”.

This story has mentioned the status of Pakistan in the climate change scenario. It has given a mention of the 2022 floods, that how it impacted the Pakistan and its people. This article has a major focus on Pakistan’s vulnerability to the climate change and relevant potential risks. The story highlighted that Pakistan is among the few top vulnerable countries to the climate change, despite its minimum contribution to the global emission. It was also mentioned that Pakistan alone can’t handle this situation. Therefore, it will need global cooperation for adapting climate change mitigation strategies.

Following pages contain deductive thematic analysis of the selected news stories from daily *The News International*;

“Climate Change Warriors’ join tree plantation drive in Swat”. (2025, April 14) *The News International*. Retrieved from: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/1301078-climate-change-warriors-join-tree-plantation-drive-in-swat>

Themes	Sub themes	Coding units in news report.
7. International Climate Discourse and Pakistan	7.1 Climate Change in Global Context.	Plantation Drive, Collective national Responsibility, individual responsibility, Recognition of the environmental importance as a developing country.
6. Public Awareness and Education	6.1 Media's Role in Raising Awareness	Plantation of native trees (Deodar and Chinar). Islam value plantation as noble act.
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.3 Role of NGOs and Civil Society	Climate Change Warriors (NGO).

Interpretation and Analysis

Drawing on the deductive thematic analysis by using coding units, the researchers have found out that the news report on plantation drive under study contains content related to the overall theme of creating awareness and public engagement for plantation to mitigate the impacts of climate change. The report also encompasses three main themes of “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events”, “Public Awareness and Education” and “International Climate Discourse and Pakistan”. Simultaneously, the sub themes covered in the reports are “Role of NGOs and Civil Society”, “Media's Role in Raising Awareness” and “Climate Change in Global Context”.

In this study the researchers intended to thematically analyze the news reporting in Pakistan regarding the climate change and its impacts. By analyzing the data, the study found that the news report in *The News International* regarding the plantation drive and environmental awareness to mitigate impacts of climate change especially in rural area like Swat depicts its commitment to the green Pakistan. The researcher found out that the news report is based on the role of local NGOs such as “Climate Change Warriors” and public in creating awareness regarding the importance of plantation and the realization of national and individual responsibilities.

By using the coding units, the researcher analyzed the content of the report and discovered that it encompasses three main themes and three sub themes. In this regard, by finding coding units in news report such as “role of NGO” and “Public Concern”

the report lies in the main theme of “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events” and the sub theme of “Role of NGOs and Civil Society”. Similarly, as the news report contains the information regarding the public awareness and environmental education, the researcher found that it encompasses the main theme of “Public Awareness and Education” and the sub theme of “Media's Role in Raising Awareness”. Because the report has included the relevant words and phrase to the coding units like “Islam value plantation as noble act” and awareness and education regarding the importance of native species such as “Chinar and Deodar” and their role in environmental sustainability.

The study also found that Pakistani media especially *The News International* place high value to environmental coverage. Additionally, by using coding units such as National Responsibilities and Plantation Drive, the study found contents in the report that explicitly relevant to the main theme of “International Climate Discourse and Pakistan” and the sub themes of “Climate Change in Global Context”. As the report contains the words and phrases such as “Plantation Drive”, “Collective national Responsibility”, “Individual responsibility”, “Recognition of the environmental importance as a developing country”.

“2022 floods caused over \$30bn losses, NA told”. (2025, May 06) *The News International*. Retrieved from: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/1308834-2022-floods-caused-over-30bn-losses-na-told>

Themes	Sub themes	Coding units in news report.
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.1 Floods and Heatwave.	Heavy Rain, Strong Wind,
1. Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events	1.2 Human Losses	Mortality.
2. Impacts on Agriculture	2.1 Agricultural Vulnerability	Agricultural Productivity Reduction, Food Security
2. Impacts on Agriculture	2.2 Water Scarcity and Management	Water Scarcity, Per Capita Water Availability,
3. Economic Implications	3.1 Economic Impact of Climate Change	Economic Loss, GDP Decline, Infrastructure Damage,
3. Economic Implications	3.2 Climate Change as a Barrier to Development	Public Health Risk, Power Outages,

Interpretation and Analysis

Drawing on the deductive thematic analysis by using coding units, the researcher has found out that the news coverage is regarding the report presented in National Assembly of Pakistan showing the losses and impacts of climate change in Pakistan. The report covers the overall theme environmental disasters and their impacts caused by climate change. The report encompasses three main themes, in which, first main theme is “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events” followed by the two sub themes “Floods and Heatwave.” And “Human Losses”. Second main theme is “Impacts on Agriculture” followed by two sub themes “Agricultural Vulnerability” and “Water Scarcity and Management”. Similarly, the third main theme is “Economic Implications” followed by two sub themes “Economic Impact of Climate Change” and “Climate Change as a Barrier to Development”. While using deductive thematic analysis, the study found that according to the news report in *The News International* presented by Ministry of Climate Change and Environmental Coordination in National Assembly of Pakistan, the country has severely and drastically affected by the severe floods in 2022. The heavy rain and flash floods resulted in heavy losses including deaths, financial losses of around \$30bn and reductions in agricultural production. By using the coding units, the researcher found that the report is overall covering three main themes followed by six sub themes. The researcher found relevant coding units such as “Heavy Rain, Strong Wind and Mortality” that covers the first main theme is “Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events” followed by the two sub themes “Floods and Heatwave.” And “Human Losses”. As the report cited NDMA that due

to sever flash floods more than 1700 people died and around 8 million people were displaced. The report further stated statistics from 2023 and 2024 heatwaves that 22 people lost their lives in Islamabad and Mardan in 2023 and 427 death tolls recorded in Karachi.

Moreover, by using the coding units such as “Agricultural Productivity Reduction, Food Security, Water Scarcity, Per Capita Water Availability”, the researcher found the report relevant to the Second main theme of “Impacts on Agriculture” followed by two sub themes “Agricultural Vulnerability” and “Water Scarcity and Management”. According to the report, owing to the disastrous floods in history, unprecedented reduction in agricultural production recorded a loss of more than \$5bn. Similarly, the researcher found the third main theme is “Economic Implications” followed by two sub themes “Economic Impact of Climate Change” and “Climate Change as a Barrier to Development” by using coding units such as “Economic Loss, GDP Decline, Infrastructure Damage, Public Health Risk and Power Outages”.

CONCLUSION

Owing to excessive human activities and changing the global weather patterns such as global warming, climate change is a phenomenon with implications on approximately all sectors around the world. Pakistan, being struggling economy, is also considered as extremely prone to the environmental disasters and crises that resulted in both human and economic losses. In this regard, we intended to explore and analyze the predominant themes available in the climate change reporting given by the prominent Pakistani newspapers during April 15th to May 14th,

2025. The researchers selected one month period to explore the coverage in *Dawn*, *Daily Times*, and *The News International*, leading Pakistani newspapers. The researchers aimed to explore how Pakistani newspapers framed climate change issue and how they linked climate change consequences to human and economic losses and how these newspapers created public awareness and educated the nations regarding the climate change. Similarly, the researchers intended to find out whether the media is relying on scientific reports or sensationalizing climate change in a way that might mislead or oversimplify the issue. Another objective of the study was to explore the media coverage of how prepared Pakistan is for extreme weather events, such as floods and droughts, and government plans to mitigate these disasters.

The data was collected from Pakistani newspapers; *Dawn*, *Daily Times*, and *The News International* for doing the deductive thematic analysis of climate change related stories. The time frame selected for the study was April 15, 2025 to May 14, 2025. The key words "Climate Change" "Global Warming" "floods" "flash floods" "terrestrial rains" "torrential rains" "land sliding" "glacier melting" "Hail Storm" were used in google advance search to collect the data and lottery sampling method was employed to select the required sample. For this study the researchers found 79 news stories regarding climate change in the *Daily Times*, 53 news stories each in daily *Dawn* and *The News International* by applying the key words and search mechanism employed in this study the time period understudy i.e. April 14th to May 14th, 2025. After employing data cleansing, we found 09 news stories relevant to the objectives of this study in *Daily Times*, 13 in *Dawn*, and 12 in daily *The News International*.

Our findings show that the news reports contained themes such as; "Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events", "Economic Implication", "Policy and Governance", "Public Awareness and Education", "Climate Justice and Social Inequality", "Policy and Governance", and "International Climate Discourse and Pakistan", "International Climate Discourse and Pakistan".

In this study, the researchers intended to explore the coverage of Pakistani newspapers; *Dawn*, *Daily Times*, and *The News International* regarding the climate change issue. In this regard, the researchers designed well-articulated questions along with themes and sub

themes to explore comprehensively. By using coding sheet, the researchers found that *Daily Times* gave more coverage to the climate change issue. The level of coverage depicts the responsible journalism of Pakistani media regarding the environmental changes and their implications. According to the findings, the researchers found the overall theme of environmental disaster reporting along with public awareness in selected news reports. By using the coding units, the researchers found that the major prevailing theme is "Environmental Disasters and Crisis Events" followed by the two sub themes "Floods and Heatwave" and "Human Losses". This theme is linked with one of the main questions of the study that how media frame environmental disaster events and how news reports link climate change consequences with human losses? According to the findings, almost in each selected news report, all the newspapers have framed environmental disaster events in an alarming way by presenting facts and figures of the events such as number of deaths, financial and infrastructure losses. Similarly, the second major theme presented in selected news reports was related to the main theme of "Public Awareness and Education" with sub themes of "Focus on Scientific Findings vs. Popular Narratives" which is linked with another main question of whether the media is relying on scientific reports or sensationalizing climate change in a way that might mislead or oversimplify the issue? By using coding units such as "Met Office Warnings, Scientific Assessment" the researchers explored that all the newspapers gave proper coverage to the alerts, information, and warnings from the Meteorological Department, NDMA, PDMA and Ministry of Climate and Environmental Coordination. According to the findings, the information given by all the authorities is based on scientific reports stating the actual statistics.

Moreover, according to the findings, the selected newspapers gave comparatively less coverage to a main theme "Policy and Governance" which is linked to the question that media coverage of how prepared Pakistan is for extreme weather events, such as floods and droughts, and government plans to mitigate these disasters? The researchers found that the news reports provided information about how the authorities including NDMA, PDMA, Meteorological departments remained active and prepared in

environmental disaster events to mitigate the impacts of the events. The reports highly focused on warnings from the Meteorological department to inform the people in affected areas. Similarly, according to the findings, other themes such as “Impacts on Agriculture” and “Economic Implications” have also been given coverage to some extent.

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